

REQUIREMENTS (Cyber Resilience Act)	IEC 62433 STANDARD	Gaps between Regulations
GENERAL	GENERAL	IEC 62443 focuses exclusively on industrial automation control systems
3.1.1 Products with digital elements shall be designed, developed, and produced in such a way as to ensure an appropriate level of cybersecurity according to the risks.	IEC 62443-3-2 Part 3-2: Security risk assessment for system design	This standard does not include concepts such as security by design.
	IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements	This standard does not include the concept of risk assessment.
3.1.2 Products with digital elements shall be delivered without known exploitable vulnerabilities.	IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements	
3.1.4 (3b) Ensure protection against unauthorized access through appropriate control mechanisms, including, but not limited to, authentication, identity, or access management systems.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	
3.1.5 (3c) Protect the confidentiality of stored, transmitted, or otherwise processed data, whether personal or otherwise, such as by encrypting relevant data at rest or in transit using state-of-the-art mechanisms.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	The confidentiality requirement is quite generic and does not provide technical details.
3.1.6 (3d) Protect the integrity of stored, transmitted, or otherwise processed data, whether personal or otherwise, commands, programs, and configurations against any unauthorized manipulation or modification by the user, as well as report corruptions.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	
3.1.8 Protect the availability of essential functions, including resilience and mitigation against denial-of-service attacks.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	

3.1.10 Be designed, developed, and produced to limit attack surfaces, including external interfaces.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	
3.1.11 Be designed, developed, and produced to reduce the impact of an incident using appropriate exploitation mitigation mechanisms and techniques.	Security for industrial automation and control systems - Part 3-2: Security risk assessment for system design	Does not explicitly mention encryption at rest or data minimization, addresses security by design, risk assessment, and secure architecture. However, it does not detail specific requirements for isolation or secure environments.
3.1.12 Provide security-related information by logging and/or monitoring relevant internal activity, including access or modification of data, services, or functions.	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	
3.1.13 Ensure that vulnerabilities can be addressed through security updates, including, where appropriate, automatic updates and notification of available updates to users.	IEC 62443-2-1 Industrial communication networks - Network and system security - Part 2-1: Establishing an industrial automation and control system security program	Does not address automatic updates and user notifications in detail.
	IEC 62443-4-2 Part 4-2: Technical security requirements for IACS components	Does not address user notifications.
3.2.2 In relation to the risks posed by products with digital elements, address and remediate vulnerabilities without delay, including providing security updates.	IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements	Does not cover aspects such as vulnerability classification, remediation, and patch management comprehensively.
3.2.4 Once a security update is available, publicly disclose information about the resolved vulnerabilities, including a description of the vulnerabilities, information enabling users to identify the affected product with digital	IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements	

<p>elements, the impacts of the vulnerabilities, their severity, and information to help users address the vulnerabilities.</p>		
<p>3.2.7 Establish mechanisms to securely distribute updates to products with digital elements to ensure that exploitable vulnerabilities are promptly corrected or mitigated.</p>	<p>IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements</p>	<p>The standard does not explicitly address publishing update hashes and providing instructions for verifying them. Organizations may need to develop additional guidelines or policies to ensure that hashes are published and that users receive clear instructions to verify the authenticity and integrity of software updates. While the standard covers secure software development practices, it does not explicitly mention the requirement to use code signing certificates to sign security updates, which ensures the issuer's identity and update integrity.</p>
<p>3.2.8 Ensure that when security patches or updates are available to address identified security issues, they are distributed without delay and free of charge, accompanied by advisory messages providing users with relevant information, including possible actions to take.</p>	<p>IEC 62443-4-1 Part 4-1: Secure product development lifecycle requirements</p>	<p>Does not specify that the security update must be free of charge.</p>